

Modeling a membrane based floating solar island in waves

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Abstract. We present further developments in the modeling of a floating membrane solar island in waves. The solar island consists of a thin, floating membrane attached to a circular, elastic floating collar. The structure is modeled as two connected bodies with different structural properties. The membrane is assumed to obey the linearized membrane equations, while the floating collar is modeled using the curved Euler-Bernoulli beam equation. Linearized potential flow theory is assumed valid. A modal approach is taken, and each mode of motion is solved for in the frequency domain. All hydrodynamic loads are modeled using generalized forces in the panel code WAMIT. The model presented in [1] is extended to include radial deformation of the floater, as well as consistent in-plane motion of the membrane. The contact loads between the membrane and floater are the main focus of the present study. Our findings indicate that in-plane motions are relatively small and have little to no effect on the out-of-plane motion. However, the magnitude of the contact force in radial direction is comparable to that of the vertical contact force, suggesting that in-plane motions, despite being small, are of importance. A sensitivity study of the membrane's modal response with respect to Young's modulus indicates that both the model and full-scale solar islands operate in the stiffness-dominated regime with respect to in-plane, flexible membrane motions.

Key words: *Floating membrane; Hydroelastic response; Floating solar;*

1. Introduction

The membrane-based floating solar island is a cost-efficient solution for floating photovoltaic panels. In addition to low cost materials, direct cooling of panels from water beneath the membrane increases efficiency. A natural concern however, is the connection loads between the membrane and the floating collar, as these are an important factor in critical failures and thereby in the design. In [1] we presented vertical connection loads, dependent on the given pretension of the membrane. In this paper, we include in-plane motion in our numerical model. Results focus on a comparison of the contact loads for the vertical and horizontal components of the contact force, as well as a sensitivity study with respect to elastic properties of membrane and floater, and the membrane's pretension.

In-plane vibrations of elastic disks have been studied for a wide range of applications, and can be applied to floating membranes. Love [2] first derived the in-plane equations of motion for a thin circular disk, and applied a Helmholtz decomposition to find the corresponding eigenmodes. Holland [3] presented normalization coefficients and modal wave numbers for the case of a thin circular disk with free edge boundary conditions. Park [4] investigated the case of a thin, clamped circular disk. More recently, Kristiansen, Grøn and Faltinsen [5] studied vertical motions of the membrane based floating solar island, utilizing free edge modes and the Lagrangian multiplier technique [6]. Zhang et al. [7] extended this to include free-edge in-plane modes, as presented by Bashmal et al. [8]. However, the Lagrangian multiplier technique requires that both bodies can take shear, something the membrane cannot. We therefore instead apply the method outlined in [1], to represent the contact forces in a physically correct manner. Clamped edge modes are chosen as our homogeneous modal basis, describing motions of the membrane obeying the homogeneous boundary condition. Free edge modes are chosen as the particular modal basis to address constraints at the boundary between the membrane and floater. This approach enables a physically consistent analysis of membrane-floater contact forces, addressing a key challenge in the modeling of floating solar islands.

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2. Theory

In static configuration, both membrane and floater lie in the $r - \theta$ plane, as shown in Figure 1. The center of the membrane is located at $(r, \theta, z) = (0, 0, 0)$, and the static shape is assumed to be such that both the membrane and the floater are perfectly circular. The torus-shaped floater is exactly half submerged such that the membrane is attached at $z = 0$ and $r = R - a = R_0$, where R is the radius of the floater's center axis, a is the collar's cross-sectional radius and R_0 is the membrane's radius. Both bodies are assumed to be of uniform mass. The floater's mass per unit length is denoted m_f , while the membrane's mass per unit area is denoted m_b . The membrane's thickness, d , is assumed small compared to its radius, such that $d/R_0 \ll 1$. We assume steady state such that all responses in the time domain can be expressed on the general form $\tilde{f}(r, \theta, t) = \Re\{f(r, \theta, \omega)e^{i\omega t}\}$. In the following, the membrane displacements, (u_r, u_θ, u_z) , and the floater displacements, (v_r, v_θ, v_z) , refer to the steady state, frequency dependent displacements. Linearized equations of motion are presented for both the membrane and the floating collar, along with the respective linearized hydrodynamic loads acting on the system. The in-plane motions of the membrane in r - and θ -directions are coupled. Due to kinematic and dynamic constraints, as well as the hydrodynamic loads acting on the system, the floater and membrane motions are also coupled. Applying the method of weighted residuals [9], we obtain a system of equations which we solve for frequency dependent modal amplitudes, along with modal contact forces between the two bodies.

2.1. Governing equations

2.1.1. Membrane equations of motion

The membrane is considered an isotropic, linear-elastic structure, with Young's modulus E and Poisson ratio ν . Equations of motion are derived by considering the static and dynamic forces acting on an infinitesimal membrane element. We assume plane stress over the entire membrane element, such that stress components perpendicular to the membrane are negligible compared to those parallel with it, a consequence of the thin plate (membrane) assumption. The forces on a membrane element are expressed using the material law, relating them to the relevant elasticity parameters and the corresponding strains. The linearized equations of motion for the membrane in r -, θ - and z -directions are found by applying Newton's second law to the membrane element. The vertical hydrodynamic loads acting on the membrane due to the presence of the membrane itself are denoted as $f_{uu,zz}^{HD}$, while $f_{uv,zr}^{HD}$ and $f_{uv,zz}^{HD}$ denote the hydrodynamic loads acting on the membrane due to the presence of the floater in r - and z -directions respectively. Note that the linearized hydrodynamic loads on the membrane in r - and θ -directions are zero. Thereby, the membrane's equations of motion are given by,

$$-\omega^2 m_b u_r - \frac{\partial T_0}{\partial r} \left(1 + \frac{u_r}{r}\right) - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(T_0 \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta}\right) - \frac{Ed}{1-\nu^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} - \frac{u_r}{r^2} + \nu \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial r \partial \theta}\right) - \frac{Ed}{2(1+\nu)} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial \theta \partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial \theta^2} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta}\right) = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$-\omega^2 m_b u_\theta - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial T_0}{\partial \theta} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(T_0 \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r}\right) - \frac{Ed}{1-\nu^2} \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + \nu \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial r \partial \theta}\right) - \frac{Ed}{2(1+\nu)} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial \theta \partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} - \frac{u_\theta}{r^2}\right) = 0, \quad (2)$$

$$-\omega^2 m_b u_z - \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(T_0 \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r}\right) - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(T_0 \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \theta}\right) = f_{uu,zz}^{HD} + f_{uv,zz}^{HD} + f_{uv,zr}^{HD}. \quad (3)$$

In the following, we assume that the membrane pretension is uniform, $T_0(r, \theta) = T_0$, such that equations (1) and (2) simplify to the equations of dynamic equilibrium in studies on thin circular disks [[4], [8]], and equation (3) simplifies to that used in studies of the membrane-floater system [[1], [5],[7]].

Figure 1 Schematic illustration of the membrane-based floating solar island.

2.1.2. The linearized contact force

When the membrane is displaced, it will, in addition to its initial pretension, T_0 , have normal stresses in the radial and circumferential directions, as well as a circumferential and a radial shear stress. Vertically, there is no such contribution, as we've assumed plane stress. However, as the displaced membrane can have a nonzero angle with respect to the $r - \theta$ plane, its dynamic tangential unit vectors gain components in the vertical direction. The contact force, in this context, refers to the forces that the rim of the membrane exerts on the connected floater, at $r = R_0$. The linearized, in- and out-of-plane contributions of the contact force, in terms of the membrane displacement at the rim, are given as,

$$f_{c,r}^{m \rightarrow f} = -\frac{Ed}{1 - \nu^2} \left(\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{\nu}{r} \left[\frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + u_r \right] \right) \Big|_{r=R_0}, \quad (4)$$

$$f_{c,\theta}^{m \rightarrow f} = -\frac{Ed}{2(1 + \nu)} \left(\frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \left[\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} - u_\theta \right] \right) \Big|_{r=R_0}, \quad (5)$$

$$f_{c,z}^{m \rightarrow f} = -T_0 \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=R_0}. \quad (6)$$

Here, the superscript $m \rightarrow f$ indicates a force on the floater induced by the membrane.

2.1.3. Floater equations of motion

The floater is assumed inextensional in the azimuthal direction, and we therefore only consider floater motions in r - and z -directions. Its equations of motion are given by the modified Euler-Bernoulli beam equation [10], such that,

$$-\omega^2 m_f v_r + \frac{EI_r}{R^4} \left(\frac{\partial^4 v_r}{\partial \theta^4} + \frac{\partial^2 v_r}{\partial \theta^2} \right) = f_{vu,rz}^{HD} + f_{vv,rr}^{HD} + f_{vv,rz}^{HD} + f_{c,r}^{m \rightarrow f}, \quad (7)$$

$$-\omega^2 m_f v_z + \frac{EI_z}{R^4} \left(\frac{\partial^4 v_z}{\partial \theta^4} + \frac{\partial^2 v_z}{\partial \theta^2} \right) - \frac{T_{ax}}{R^2} \frac{\partial^2 v_z}{\partial \theta^2} = f_{vu,zz}^{HD} + f_{vv,zr}^{HD} + f_{vv,zz}^{HD} + f_{c,z}^{m \rightarrow f}, \quad (8)$$

where $f_{vv,rr}^{HD}$ and $f_{vv,rz}^{HD}$ denote the radial loads on the floater due to floater motion in r - and z -directions respectively. Similarly, $f_{vv,zr}^{HD}$ and $f_{vv,zz}^{HD}$ denote the vertical loads on the floater due to floater motion in r - and z -directions. The terms, $f_{vu,zz}^{HD}$ and $f_{vu,rz}^{HD}$ denote the loads on the floater in radial and vertical directions due to vertical motion of the membrane. Note that the contact force due to motions of the membrane is included as the last term on the right hand side.

2.1.4. Boundary conditions at membrane-floater interface

Two sets of conditions at the boundary describe the connection at the membrane-floater interface: a kinematic constraint requiring the membrane's rim to be at the same position as the floater at all times, and a dynamic constraint requiring the force exerted on the membrane by the floater to be equal and opposite to the force exerted on the floater by the membrane. We can express this as follows,

$$(v_r, v_\theta, v_z) = (u_r, u_\theta, u_z)|_{r=R_0}, \quad (9)$$

$$(f_{c,r}^{f \rightarrow m}, f_{c,\theta}^{f \rightarrow m}, f_{c,z}^{f \rightarrow m}) = - (f_{c,r}^{m \rightarrow f}, f_{c,\theta}^{m \rightarrow f}, f_{c,z}^{m \rightarrow f}) \Big|_{r=R_0}. \quad (10)$$

To enforce both kinematic and dynamic conditions, we separate the membrane motion in two sets of modes, referred to as homogeneous and particular modes. The homogeneous modes satisfy a chosen homogeneous boundary condition, while the particular modes ensure the membrane's connection to the floater.

2.2. The floater modal representation

The floater motions are represented as a Fourier series, truncated at M_h horizontal modes and M_v vertical modes,

$$v_r = \sum_{m=1}^{M_h} E_m^{(in.)} \cos m\theta, \quad (11)$$

$$v_\theta = - E_1^{(in.)} \sin \theta, \quad (12)$$

$$v_z = \sum_{m=0}^{M_v} E_m^{(out.)} \cos m\theta, \quad (13)$$

where $E_m^{(in.)}$ and $E_m^{(out.)}$ are unknown modal amplitudes. The superscripts *in.* and *out.* refer to in-plane (horizontal) and out-of-plane (vertical), as do the subscripts *h* and *v* of the truncation numbers. Note that we only have one component in the azimuthal direction. This mode will, together with the $m = 1$ component in radial direction, correspond to surge, such that $\eta_1 = E_1^{(in.)}$. The floater is assumed stiff in the azimuthal direction, so all other in-plane elastic modes are radial deformations. The vertical $m = 1$ mode is similar to pitch, $\eta_5 \simeq E_1^{out.}$, while the vertical $m = 0$ mode corresponds to heave, $\eta_3 = E_0^{out.}$.

2.3. In-plane membrane modes

The in-plane equations of motion are decoupled using a Helmholtz decomposition to find suitable eigenmodes, as first derived by Love [2]. A more detailed derivation can be found in Park [4]. The resulting in-plane modes are on the same form as those used in both [7] and [8]. We define the parameters $E^* = \frac{Ed}{1-\nu^2}$ and $G = \frac{Ed}{2(1+\nu)}$. The generic modal wave numbers are defined as $k_{mn}^{(1)} = m_b \omega_{mn}^2 / E^*$ and $k_{mn}^{(2)} = m_b \omega_{mn}^2 / G$, where the modal frequencies ω_{mn} are determined by the chosen condition at the boundary, $r = R_0$. Modal representations in r - and θ -directions for every m 'th azimuthal index and every n 'th radial index are vectorial,

$$\vec{\psi}_{mn} = \begin{bmatrix} \psi_{mn}^{(r)} \\ \psi_{mn}^{(\theta)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \left(A_{mn} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} J_m(k_{mn}^{(1)} r) + B_{mn} \frac{m}{r} J_m(k_{mn}^{(2)} r) \right) \cos m\theta \\ - \left(A_{mn} \frac{m}{r} J_m(k_{mn}^{(1)} r) + B_{mn} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} J_m(k_{mn}^{(2)} r) \right) \sin m\theta \end{bmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

where terms associated with A_{mn} describe dilational displacement (a change in area of the membrane), while the terms associated with B_{mn} describe shear (a change in shape, without a change in area) [3].

2.3.1. Modal boundary conditions

In the following, we choose a homogeneous modal basis that enforces zero displacement at the rim of the membrane, while allowing for a nonzero force at the boundary (referred to as clamped edge modes). The particular modes, in contrast, are chosen such that they give no contribution to forces exerted on the floater, but allow for a displacement at the rim. For in-plane particular modes, a slight variation of this is applied, to account for the fact that we assume zero azimuthal displacement of the floater. A combined condition enforcing zero radial force while maintaining zero azimuthal displacement is used. Consequently, both homogeneous and particular in-plane modes are clamped in the azimuthal direction, while only the radial component of the particular modes contribute to displacement at the boundary. This ensures that the rim of the membrane follows the attached floater at all times, and is equivalent to the approach referred to as Method 1 in [1]. The chosen in-plane conditions at the rim result in two equations that can be expressed on matrix form in terms of the normalization coefficients, A_{mn} and B_{mn} , in equation (14). By requiring the determinant of the resulting matrix to be zero, we obtain the corresponding frequency equation. We define the in-plane clamped edge modal wave numbers as $k_{mn}^{(1)} = \lambda_{mn}^{(1)}$ and $k_{mn}^{(2)} = \lambda_{mn}^{(2)}$, where the indices refer to the n 'th root of the m 'th order frequency equation. The modal wave numbers for the combined boundary condition are found in a similar manner (see [3] or [8] for full derivations of an analogous case). These are denoted as $k_{mn}^{(1)} = \mu_{mn}^{(1)}$ and $k_{mn}^{(2)} = \mu_{mn}^{(2)}$.

2.3.2. Normalization of modes

Elasticity problems will, in general, give eigenmodes which are orthogonal [3], such that the inner product of two modes is nonzero only if $m = p$ and $n = q$. To make use of this in the following Galerkin approach, we normalize the modes such that the nonzero values of the inner product equate to the membrane's area. The chosen modal boundary condition will give the second relation needed to solve for the normalization coefficients A_{mn} and B_{mn} . We denote normalization coefficients for the clamped and free edge boundary conditions as $A_{mn}^{(c)}$ and $B_{mn}^{(c)}$, and $A_{mn}^{(f)}$ and $B_{mn}^{(f)}$ respectively. Note that the normalization coefficients are of units m, such that each mode is dimensionless.

2.3.3. The in-plane modal representation

The in-plane motion is represented by a truncated sum of N_h homogeneous modes and one particular mode for each m 'th order in-plane mode. The number of m modes must equal the number of in-plane floater modes, truncated at M_h . The total in-plane displacement is given by,

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_r \\ u_\theta \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{m=1}^{M_h} \sum_{n=1}^{N_h} C_{mn}^{(H)} \begin{bmatrix} \psi_{mn}^{(r,H)} \\ \psi_{mn}^{(\theta,H)} \end{bmatrix} + \sum_{m=1}^{M_h} C_m^{(P)} \begin{bmatrix} \psi_m^{(r,P)} \\ \psi_m^{(\theta,P)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (15)$$

As the in-plane membrane modes are vectorial due to structurally coupled equations of motion, the r - and θ -components of the modal representation share a common unknown modal amplitude, denoted $C_{mn}^{(H)}$ for the homogeneous modes, and $C_m^{(P)}$ for the particular modes. Both homogeneous and particular modes are on the form of equation (14), but with different modal wave numbers satisfying different modal boundary conditions. The particular modes are scaled such that the r -dependent component equates to 1 at the boundary in r - and z -directions. This implies that the membrane's particular modal coefficients are equal to the floater's modal coefficients, such that $C_m^{(P)} = E_m^{(in.)}$, thereby reducing the number of unknowns in our system. For every m , we chose the first radial mode ($n = 1$) as the m 'th particular mode. The total in-plane motion is represented as,

$$\begin{aligned} u_r = \eta_1 \cos \theta + \sum_{m=1}^{M_h} \sum_{n=1}^{N_h} C_{mn}^{(H)} \left(A_{mn}^{(c)} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} J_m(\lambda_{mn}^{(1)} r) + B_{mn}^{(c)} \frac{m}{r} J_m(\lambda_{mn}^{(2)} r) \right) \cos m\theta \\ + \sum_{m=2}^{M_h} E_m^{(in.)} \Gamma_m^{-1} \left(A_{m1}^{(f)} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} J_m(\mu_{m1}^{(1)} r) + B_{m1}^{(f)} \frac{m}{r} J_m(\mu_{m1}^{(2)} r) \right) \cos m\theta, \quad (16) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
u_\theta = & -\eta_1 \sin \theta - \sum_{m=1}^{M_h} \sum_{n=1}^{N_h} C_{mn}^{(H)} \left(A_{mn}^{(c)} \frac{m}{r} J_m(\lambda_{mn}^{(1)} r) + B_{mn}^{(c)} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} J_m(\lambda_{mn}^{(2)} r) \right) \sin m\theta \\
& - \sum_{m=2}^{M_h} E_m^{(in.)} \Gamma_m^{-1} \left(A_{m1}^{(f)} \frac{m}{r} J_m(\mu_{m1}^{(1)} r) + B_{m1}^{(f)} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} J_m(\mu_{m1}^{(2)} r) \right) \sin m\theta, \quad (17)
\end{aligned}$$

where,

$$\Gamma_m = A_{m1}^{(f)} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} J_m(\mu_{m1}^{(1)} R_0) + B_{m1}^{(f)} \frac{m}{R_0} J_m(\mu_{m1}^{(2)} R_0). \quad (18)$$

Note the special case of the $m = 1$ modes. We replace the standard free edge particular mode, with surge, expressed in polar coordinates as $\vec{\eta}_1 = \eta_1 (\cos \theta, -\sin \theta)$. The kinematic constraint requires surge motion of the membrane to be equal to surge motion of the floater. As discussed in Farag and Pan [11], the $m = 1$ elastic clamped edge modes are the only membrane modes that account for membrane displacement at the center, independent of the floater motion (in surge). These modes will also contribute to the contact force.

2.4. Out-of-plane membrane modes

As the vertical membrane motion is not structurally coupled to the in-plane membrane motion, we can define its modal representation separately. We decompose the motion in the same manner, defining homogeneous and particular modes such that,

$$u_z = \sum_{m=0}^{M_v} \sum_{n=1}^{N_v} D_{mn}^{(H)} \psi_{mn}^{(z,H)} + \sum_{m=0}^{M_v} D_m^{(P)} \psi_{m1}^{(z,P)}. \quad (19)$$

The out-of-plane modes are of Fourier-Bessel type, equivalent to those used in [1], defined as $\psi_{mn}^{(z)} = J_m(k_{mn}^{(3)} r) \cos m\theta$, where $k_{mn}^{(3)}$ is a generic modal wave number determined by the chosen modal condition at the boundary $r = R_0$. We apply the same modal boundary conditions as for the in-plane modes, defining the homogeneous modes as clamped edge and the particular modes as free edge. The clamped edge out-of-plane modal wave number, satisfies $J_m(k_{mn}^{(3)} R_0) = 0$, and is denoted $k_{mn}^{(3)} = \lambda_{mn}^{(3)}$. The free edge out-of-plane modal wave number satisfies $\frac{\partial}{\partial r} J_m(k_{mn}^{(3)} R_0) = 0$, and is denoted $k_{mn}^{(3)} = \mu_{mn}^{(3)}$. The particular mode is scaled by it's value at the rim, such that $D_m^{(P)} = E_m^{(out.)}$. The total out-of-plane motion is thereby,

$$u_z = \sum_{m=0}^{M_v} \sum_{n=1}^{M_v} D_{mn}^{(H)} J_m(\lambda_{mn}^{(3)} r) \cos m\theta + \sum_{m=0}^{M_v} E_m^{(out.)} \frac{J_m(\mu_{m1}^{(3)} r)}{J_m(\mu_{m1}^{(3)} R_0)} \cos m\theta. \quad (20)$$

In total there are $(M_v + 1)N_v$ unknown homogeneous modal amplitudes, $D_{mn}^{(H)}$, and $M_v + 1$ unknown floater modal amplitudes, $E_m^{(out.)}$.

2.5. The system matrix

We insert the membrane and floater modal representations into the governing equations of motion, and apply the method of weighted residuals as in [9]. The operator (i.e. from the equation of motion) acting on each mode can be written as a product of that mode with its modal wave number squared, greatly reducing the complexity of the equations. As our modes are orthogonal, integrals with modal indices $m \neq p$ or $n \neq q$ will evaluate to zero. The membrane and floater equations are coupled structurally through the contact forces, but also hydrodynamically through hydrodynamic loads on the right hand side. Consider the m 'th in-plane part of our system,

$$\begin{bmatrix} K_{m1}^{(H)} & \cdots & 0 & K_{m1}^{(P)} \\ 0 & \ddots & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & K_{mN_h}^{(H)} & K_{mN_h}^{(P)} \\ F_{m1}^{(c,r)} & \cdots & F_{mN_h}^{(c,r)} & K_m^{(f,r)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_{m1}^{(H)} \\ \vdots \\ C_{mN_h}^{(H)} \\ E_m^{(in.)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ F_m^{(vr,HD)} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (21)$$

The hydrodynamic loads are (for now) all on the right hand side of the equation, and are nonzero for the floater equation only. The system will be of size $(N_h + 1) \times (N_h + 1)$, where the first N_h rows correspond to the membrane equation projected onto N_h homogeneous modes. We define the matrix elements of this part as,

$$K_{mn}^{(H)} = \left(-\omega^2 m_b + E^* \lambda_{mn}^{(1)2} \right) \pi R_0^2 = -M_b (\omega^2 - \omega_{mn,H}^2), \quad (22)$$

$$K_{mn}^{(P)} = \left(-\omega^2 m_b + E^* \mu_{m1}^{(1)2} \right) \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{R_0} \vec{\psi}_{m1}^{(P)} \cdot \vec{\psi}_{mn}^{(H)} r \, dr d\theta = -m_b I_{mn} (\omega^2 - \omega_{m1,P}^2), \quad (23)$$

where $I_{mn} = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{R_0} \vec{\psi}_{m1}^{(P)} \cdot \vec{\psi}_{mn}^{(H)} r \, dr d\theta$ and $M_b = m_b \pi R_0^2$ is the total membrane mass. The last row of the in-plane system matrix corresponds to the floater equation of motion projected onto mode m , where $K_m^{(f,r)} = -\omega^2 m_f \pi R + \frac{EI}{R^4} (m^4 - m^2) \pi R$ and terms $F_{m1}^{(c,r)}, \dots, F_{mN_h}^{(c,r)}$ are the N_h components of the contact force in mode m . These are found by inserting modal representations (16) and (17) into equation (4). Note that the particular mode in θ -direction gives a contribution to the contact force, because it is forced to maintain zero displacement at the boundary (as the floater is assumed inextensional). Since the homogeneous modes are orthogonal, and as there are no in-plane hydrodynamic loads on the membrane, we can write all homogeneous in-plane modal coefficients in terms of the m 'th radial modal coefficient of the floater, such that,

$$C_{mn}^{(H)} = -\frac{K_{mn}^{(P)}}{K_{mn}^{(H)}} E_m^{(in.)}. \quad (24)$$

The m 'th out-of-plane system can, in a similar manner, be written as,

$$\begin{bmatrix} Q_{m1}^{(H)} & \cdots & 0 & Q_{m1}^{(P)} \\ 0 & \ddots & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & Q_{mN_v}^{(H)} & Q_{mN_v}^{(P)} \\ F_{m1}^{(c,z)} & \cdots & F_{mN_v}^{(c,z)} & K_m^{(f,z)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} D_{m1}^{(H)} \\ \vdots \\ D_{mN_v}^{(H)} \\ E_m^{(out.)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} F_{m1}^{(uz,HD)} \\ \vdots \\ F_{mN_v}^{(uz,HD)} \\ F_m^{(vz,HD)} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (25)$$

The N_v diagonal terms, $Q_{m1}^{(H)}, \dots, Q_{mN_v}^{(H)}$, due to contributions from homogeneous modes are given as,

$$Q_{mn}^{(H)} = \begin{cases} 2\pi \left(-\omega^2 m_b + T_0 \lambda_{mn}^{(3)2} \right) & \text{for } m = 0, \\ \pi \left(-\omega^2 m_b + T_0 \lambda_{mn}^{(3)2} \right) & \text{for } m > 0. \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

The contribution from the particular mode is given by the column vector with elements, $Q_{m1}^{(P)}, \dots, Q_{mN_v}^{(P)}$, defined as,

$$Q_{mn}^{(P)} = \left(-\omega^2 m_b + T_0 \mu_{m1}^{(3)2} \right) \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{R_0} \psi_{m1}^{(z,P)} \psi_{mn}^{(z,H)} r \, dr d\theta. \quad (27)$$

Table 1 Parameters from model tests (2023) in NTNU's small towing tank. The model is of scale 1:50.

Parameter	Notation	Value	Unit
Membrane diameter	$2R_0$	1.17	m
Membrane thickness	d	0.13	mm
Membrane mass	m_b	0.18	kg m ⁻²
Membrane pretension	T_0	15.0	Nm ⁻¹
Membrane elasticity	E	3.7×10^6	Nm ⁻²
Membrane Poisson ratio	ν	0.45	–
Floater center-line diameter	$2R$	1.20	m
Floater cross-sectional diameter	$2a$	0.03	m
Floater mass	m_f	0.34	kg m ⁻¹
Floater axial tension	T_{ax}	1.80	N
Floater bending stiffness	EI	0.50	Nm ²
OQUS reflective sphere mass	$m_{oq.}$	0.004	kg
Tank width		2.5	m
Water depth	h	0.7	m

The last row of the system matrix, corresponding to the m 'th out-of-plane floater equation, consists of mass and stiffness terms given by,

$$K_m^{(f,z)} = -\omega^2 m_f \pi R + \left[\frac{EI}{R^4} (m^4 - m^2) - T_{ax} m^2 \right] \pi R, \quad (28)$$

as well as the vertical contact forces, through matrix elements $F_{m1}^{(c,z)}, \dots, F_{mN_v}^{(c,z)}$. The sum of these correspond to the m 'th contact force given in equation (6), projected onto the m 'th floater mode.

When we later refer the *coupled* system of equations, we mean the system where these in- and out-of-plane systems are coupled, that is, when there are hydrodynamic loads in the radial equation of motion due to vertical motions and vice versa. Coupling between membrane and floater is always implied. The only addition to the m 'th out-of-plane system to include coupling with in-plane motions is the m 'th in-plane floater equation of motion in radial direction, with additional stiffness and inertia terms due to the presence of the membrane. The complete m 'th system of equations is given by,

$$\begin{bmatrix} Q_{m1}^{(H)} & \dots & 0 & Q_{m1}^{(P)} & 0 \\ 0 & \ddots & 0 & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & Q_{mN_v}^{(H)} & Q_{mN_v}^{(P)} & 0 \\ F_{m1}^{(c,z)} & \dots & F_{mN_v}^{(c,z)} & K_m^{(f,z)} & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \tilde{K}_m^{(f,r)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} D_{m1}^{(H)} \\ \vdots \\ D_{mN}^{(H)} \\ E_m^{(out.)} \\ E_m^{(in.)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} F_{mn}^{(uz,HD)} \\ \vdots \\ F_m^{(uz,HD)} \\ F_m^{(vz,HD)} \\ F_m^{(vr,HD)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (29)$$

where the right hand side now also includes hydrodynamic coupling terms between in- and out-of-plane loads on membrane and floater. The floater radial equation now also accounts for in-plane membrane motion as,

$$\tilde{K}_m^{(f,r)} = K_m^{(f,r)} - \sum_{n=1}^{N_h} F_{mn}^{(c,r)} \frac{K_{mn}^{(P)}}{K_{mn}^{(H)}}. \quad (30)$$

Figure 2 Model tests in NTNU’s small towing tank, June 2023. The incident waves approach from the right hand side. Photos are ordered in decreasing wave length (and increasing wavenumber).

3. Results and discussion

During the summer of 2023, model tests of a 1:50 scale floating solar island were performed in NTNU’s small towing tank. Selected photos are shown in Figure 2. A description of the experimental setup can be found in [1]. The corresponding model scale parameters are presented in Table 1, where we’ve now included the Young’s modulus of model’s membrane fabric, based on tensile tests (Muhammad Mukhlas Sabara, personal communication). All experimental results presented in this paper were obtained using Qualisys’ optical motion capture system (OQUS infrared cameras). In [1], a comparison of experimental point RAOs compared well with estimates from the theoretical model (including only vertical motions), but there were some discrepancies hypothesized to be due to coupling with in-plane motion. We investigate this in the following. All the numerical results are computed using model scale parameters in Table 1. All hydrodynamic loads are computed using the lower-order method and generalized modes in the panel code WAMIT 7.5, with both finite water depth and tank wall effects included. The complete system is solved in MATLAB, with 420 vertical membrane modes, 20 vertical and 20 horizontal floater modes. The 420 in-plane membrane modes are included through equation (30). For 300 incident wave frequencies the system is solved in less than 2 seconds (after importing hydrodynamic loads). While the MATLAB code has not been fully optimized, this demonstrates the computational efficiency of the frequency-domain approach compared to more costly alternatives such as time-domain potential flow coupled with finite element analysis.

3.1. Effects of hydrodynamic coupling between in- and out of plane motions

Due to the assumption of linearity, no in-plane hydrodynamic loads act on the membrane. The in-plane excitation of the membrane is purely due to its connection with the floater. The floater, on the other hand, will experience in-plane hydrodynamic loads. These are in general hydrodynamically coupled with vertical hydrodynamic loads on both floater and membrane. This is the only source of coupling that exists between in- and out-of-plane motions, as the linearized structural equations for the in-plane and out-of-plane motions are decoupled. Figure 3 a) and b) presents floater modal RAOs for the coupled in- and out-of-plane systems, compared with results where vertical and horizontal motions are solved for separately, and thus, with no hydrodynamic coupling. The out-of-plane motion is in general negligibly affected by the coupling with in-plane motions. The in-plane motion is, on the other hand, largely affected by the out-of-plane motion. The hydrodynamic coupling with vertical modes will introduce cancellations at the same frequencies as for the vertical motion. Without vertical motion, the membrane will act as a lid. Allowing for a coupling with vertical motion allows for the membrane to follow the incident wave, giving corresponding cancellation points as for the out-of-plane motions. Similar effects occur for in- and out-of-plane membrane modes, shown in Figure 3 c) and d). Only for the $m = 1$ out-of-plane membrane modes do we observe some discrepancies in results from coupled and uncoupled system, for the highest considered kR . This is due to coupling with surge, which is by far the most dominant in-plane mode of motion.

Figure 3 Membrane and floater modal RAOs for in- and out-of-plane motion, with and without coupling between out-of-plane and in-plane motions respectively.

Figure 4 Elastic, in-plane point motion RAOs of the membrane as a function of the non-dimensional wavenumber kR , with and without tank-wall effects, for two points at $\theta = \pi/2$. A total of $N_v = N_h = 20$ radial modes and $M_v = M_h = 19$ azimuthal modes are included.

3.2. Point motions and tank wall effects

In the following we denote the elastic motions as \vec{u}' , such that the total in-plane motion is, $\vec{u} = \vec{\eta}_1 + \vec{u}'$. Figure 4 shows computed elastic radial and azimuthal membrane point motion RAOs, with and without tank-wall effects, for a range of incident wave frequencies. Note the small values on the vertical axis, of order 10^{-4} - 10^{-3} . The tank-wall effects on the in-plane motions are significant, as for the out-of-plane motions [1]. As the radial distance from the center increases (from left to right) the elastic radial in-plane motion increases. This is because the radial deformation of the membrane is due to the floater's radial deformation at the rim. As we consider points further away from the floater (closer to the center), the membrane will feel deformations of the floater less, since we are in the stiffness dominated regime. The fact that the in-plane membrane motions are stiffness dominated for the considered wave numbers, is discussed later. The floater is assumed to have zero elastic motion in the azimuthal direction, and so the azimuthal motion of the membrane will decrease for points closer to the rim. Azimuthal motion of the membrane is only directly coupled with the floater motion through the rigid body surge mode, corresponding to the $m = 1$ in-plane particular membrane mode. Other azimuthal motion of the membrane is due to its coupling with radial membrane motions. Azimuthal motion along the membrane's centerline at $\theta = \pi$ will be zero, as it is proportional to $\sin m\theta$.

Figure 5 shows a comparison of out-of-plane point motion RAOs from model tests, with present results for vertical motions, with and without coupling with in-plane motions. Note that the results for uncoupled vertical motion are identical to those presented in [1], except with higher precision values of the modal wave numbers, which do not change the results visually. Some of the observed discrepancies between the numerical and experimental results were hypothesized to be due to coupling with in-plane motions. However, this is not the case, as shown in Figure 5. The out-of-plane membrane motions are only insignificantly affected by the coupling with in-plane motions. There are several possible alternative explanations for the differences observed at lower frequencies (especially around $kR \simeq 3$ for up-wave point on floater, $\theta = \pi$). One candidate is the piecewise increased axial tension of the floater, due to mooring pretension. Mooring loads are not included in our present, but could be represented by radial point loads acting on the floater. This will be investigated in future work. Another alternative explanation of discrepancies at low kR is viscous effects, also the topic of future work. There is considerable relative horizontal motion between the water and the floater, meaning flow separation given the present wave conditions, with viscous loads as a consequence.

Figure 5 Computed out-of-plane point motion RAOs of floater (left) and membrane (right) as a function of the non-dimensional wavenumber kR , with (solid line) and without (dashed line) tank-wall effects. A total of $N_v = N_h = 20$ radial modes and $M_v = M_h = 19$ azimuthal modes are included. Experimental results for two different wave steepnesses are shown for comparison. The model particulars are given in Table 1.

3.3. Contact forces

Figure 6 shows a comparison of horizontal and vertical contact forces for selected incident wave frequencies, given by equations (4)-(6). The vertical contact force, $f_{(c,z)}$, depending on the membrane's pretension, T_0 , is in general larger than horizontal contact forces, which depend on elasticity parameters. However, the radial contact force is still significant and of similar order of magnitude as the vertical contact force. Especially at the up-wave part of the structure ($\theta = \pi$), the radial contact force is larger or of similar magnitude to the vertical contact force. This may be surprising given the very low magnitude of in-plane motions (Figures 3(c) and 4). However, as the membrane's Young's modulus, E , is of order 10^6 , small elastic in-plane motions can result in large forces at the connection, even for a very thin membrane as in the present work, with $d = 0.00013\text{m}$. The contact force in azimuthal direction, $f_{(c,\theta)}$, is much smaller than the contact force in radial direction, $f_{(c,r)}$, because we have neglected all elastic azimuthal deformation of the floater. Surge ($m = 1$) is the only floater mode with an azimuthal component. In contrast, the floater exhibits elastic motions in the radial direction for all m . For increasing incident wave frequencies, the contact forces vary more rapidly around the rim as higher Fourier m -modes are excited.

Figure 6 A comparison of computed horizontal and vertical contact forces at the membrane-floater boundary for selected frequencies, kR , without tank-wall effects. The contact force is made non-dimensional by the membrane's pretension, T_0 , and given per unit amplitude, ζ_a , of the incident wave. A total of $N_v = N_h = 20$ radial modes and $M_v = M_h = 19$ azimuthal modes are included.

(a) Convergence study of m -modes, for in-plane point motion RAO and contact force at $\theta = \pi/4$. Line colors blue to red indicate an increasing truncation number, $M_h = M_v$. The number of n -modes is fixed at $N_h = N_v = 20$.

(b) Convergence study of n -modes, for in-plane point motion RAO and contact force at $\theta = \pi/4$. Line colors blue to red indicate an increasing truncation number, N_h . The truncation number of m -modes is fixed at $M_h = M_v = 19$. The number of n -modes for vertical motion is fixed at $N_v = 20$.

Figure 7 Study of modal convergence, for in-plane point motion RAO and contact force at $\theta = \pi/4$. The contact force is made non-dimensional by the membrane's pretension, T_0 , and given per unit amplitude, ζ_a , of the incident wave.

3.4. Convergence

A convergence study was conducted to determine the number of modes necessary to adequately approximate the in-plane membrane motion and the contact forces. This was achieved through a visual observation of a decreasing difference in resulting point motion or contact forces with an increasing number of modes, as shown in Figure 7. A similar study was performed in [1] for the convergence of the vertical contact force. It is important to note that, since the in-plane motions are coupled with vertical motions for every m , increasing the number of m -modes in-plane will affect the vertical motions, and increasing the number of m -modes vertically will affect the in-plane motions. Therefore, the number of in and out-of-plane m -modes are always kept equal. In [1], we observed that fewer modes were required for computing motions than for computing contact forces. However, this is not the case for in-plane motion. The radial contact force converges faster in number of n -modes, and seems to be largely accounted for by lower n -modes for every m . The point motion RAOs converge slower in m as we evaluate points closer to the rim. This is because the number of particular modes, ensuring that the membrane's rim is at the same position as the floater, is equal to the number of m -modes. Closer to the center (not shown here), the homogeneous modes will describe more of the membrane motion and fewer m -modes are needed.

Figure 8 A sensitivity study of the computed response on the first in-plane elastic clamped edge membrane mode $|C_{11}^{(H)} / \zeta_a|$ (indicated by values on contour lines), for a variation of the membrane's Young's modulus, E . Red curves indicate the first three (dry) natural frequencies for $m = 1$.

3.5. Effects of the membrane's Young's Modulus

When the incident wave frequency, ω , equates to any of the homogeneous modal natural frequencies, $\omega_{mn,H}$, the corresponding modal amplitude, $C_{mn}^{(H)}$, tends to infinity (see equations (22) and (24)). This means we have resonances of the in-plane membrane motion, and consequently large connection forces. To avoid this, the design of the solar island must be such that the natural frequencies of the membrane are well outside the relevant range of incident wave frequencies. This can be done by choosing the appropriate combination of the membrane's mass, thickness, Young's modulus and Poisson ratio. Figure 8 shows how the first elastic, clamped in-plane mode responds to variations of Young's modulus, E , and incident wave frequency, kR , as computed by our linear model. The color scale from white to blue indicates an increasing modal response, while red curves mark resonance. These are obtained by expressing the membrane's natural frequencies in terms of the non-dimensional wavenumber, substituting them into the finite water depth dispersion relation and solving iteratively for k . This is repeated for a range of Young's modulus values (see Section 2.3. for details on how the natural frequency depends on Young's modulus). Young's modulus of the membrane used in model tests is indicated by the vertical blue line, placed well into the stiffness dominated regime. In practice, membrane-like materials of Young's modulus lower than 10^6 would not be feasible for our application.

Table 2 compares natural frequencies for a selection of the lowest order clamped edge (homogeneous) modes, at model scale and full scale. The full-scale solar island will typically have a PVC-coated fabric, with Young's modulus $E \simeq 1450$ MPa, Poisson ratio $\nu = 0.08$ and thickness $d = 1$ mm (Hanseop Shin, personal communication). Applying Froude scaling gives a comparable value of Ed to that of the membrane fabric used in our model tests, assuming a model scale 1:50. The full-scale membrane has a mass per area of about 1 kg m^{-2} , so its in-plane eigenfrequencies will, though significantly lower, still be outside the relevant range of incident wave frequencies. In Table 2 we also consider the case of an increased uniform mass per unit area of the membrane, corresponding to the mass per unit area of a solar panel, assumed to be 50 kgm^{-2} , in full scale. This does not lower the eigen-frequencies of the membrane's in-plane motion enough to enter the relevant incident wave frequency range. Note that this is a rather crude simplification of the effects of adding solar panels, as the mass is not evenly distributed and as they do not have the same elastic properties as the membrane. Modeling these effects is left for future work.

3.6. Effects of the floater's bending stiffness

Figure 9 shows a comparison of contact forces in r -, θ - and z -directions for a large range of values of the floater bending stiffness, EI , and for three different incident wave frequencies, kR . For $kR = 1$, the incident wave is more than three times longer than than the structure's diameter, and the contact forces are, in general, low. We observe that only the out-of-plane contact force is affected significantly by a change in the floater bending stiffness. As $EI \rightarrow \infty$, we would expect the floater's elastic modes to approach zero, and the floater to be rigid. As elastic modes are more prevalent at higher incident wave frequencies, we see an increasing effect of the change in bending stiffness as the incident wave frequency increases.

Figure 9 A sensitivity study of the computed contact force with respect to the floater's bending stiffness, EI . The contact force is made non-dimensional by the membrane's pretension, T_0 , and given per unit amplitude, ζ_a , of the incident wave. A total of $N_v = N_h = 20$ n -modes and $M_v = M_h = 19$ m -modes are included.

Table 2 A comparison of dry natural frequencies for selected clamped edge modes, using model and full scale parameters.

$m = 1$	Model scale (Hz)	Full scale (Hz)	Full scale w. panels (Hz)	$m = 2$	Model scale (Hz)	Full scale (Hz)	Full scale w. panels (Hz)
$n = 1$	547.1	100.9	14.1	$n = 1$	834.8	153.9	21.6
$n = 2$	822.0	151.6	21.2	$n = 2$	1076.7	198.5	27.8
$n = 3$	1293.6	238.5	33.4	$n = 3$	1513.4	279.1	39.1

3.7. Effects of the membrane's pretension

The effects of the membrane's pretension, T_0 , on the contact forces in the r - and z -directions are illustrated in Figure 10. The contact force in the θ -direction is excluded here, as it is comparatively much smaller. Note the differences in the magnitude of the radial and vertical contact forces. In general, the vertical contact force is significantly more sensitive to changes in pretension than the radial contact force. This is expected, as the vertical contact force is directly related to the pretension. The radial contact force is affected by the membrane pretension only through the hydrodynamic coupling between the vertical and radial motions of the floater and membrane. The sensitivity of the contact forces in both directions increases with increasing incident wave frequency. At low wave frequencies, $kR \rightarrow 0$, the waves are long relative to the structure's diameter, and the contact forces decrease as both bodies (membrane and floater) move primarily in heave. As $T_0 \rightarrow \infty$, the membrane becomes infinitely stiff in the vertical direction, causing the vertical flexible modes to approach zero, analogous to the floater with infinite bending stiffness.

In the absence of pretension, $T_0 \rightarrow 0$, the membrane goes slack. This violates the assumptions of a linear elastic model, as the premise of small deviations from the static position is no longer valid. Assuming an incident wave height of $\zeta_a = 0.1$, m, the radial contact force equals or exceeds the pretension for $kR > 6$ and $T_0 = 5$, Nm^{-1} (see Figure 10). Even at the pretension used in model tests, $T_0 = 15$ Nm^{-1} , the radial contact force nearly equals the pretension for $kR = 12$. This highlights the importance of the radial contact force, as its magnitude relative to the pretension indicates whether the linear model remains valid.

3.8. Nonlinear effects

Although not included in the present numerical model, we lastly note the importance of nonlinear effects. Mukhlas et al. [12] showed a set-down effect for the membrane-based closed flexible fish cage, that decreases or completely removes the pretension of the membrane, given by an overfilling inside the cage. As exemplified in the previous section, the membrane-based solar island can also lose its pretension in incident waves. A membrane without pretension can lead to snap loads and other nonlinear phenomena outside the scope of the present theory. In addition to this, ongoing analysis from our model tests (not presented here) reveal significant 2ω effects for the in-plane motion of the membrane. Li [10] similarly observed important second and third order components of vertical accelerations of a floating collar (without a membrane). Lastly, viscous effects are another type of nonlinearity that we have not considered in the present model. For large relative motions between the water and floater, these effects could become important. It seems quite clear that a linear model for marine membrane structures is not adequate in practical engineering. Still, a linear model such as the one presented here is a useful benchmark case, and can be used for future validation of more complex models.

Figure 10 A sensitivity study of the computed contact force with respect to the membrane's pretension, T_0 . Note that the contact force is given per unit amplitude, ζ_a , of the incident wave. A total of $N_v = N_h = 20$ n -modes and $M_v = M_h = 19$ m -modes are included.

4. Conclusions

The model presented in [1], for a membrane-based floating solar island, is extended to include in-plane motions of the membrane, and radial deformations of the floater. A parameter study of the membrane's Young's modulus, E , shows that in-plane natural frequencies in practice are much higher than relevant wave frequencies, which is beneficial. In general, results indicate that in-plane motions have little to no effect on the out-of-plane motion, and are less than 1% of the incident wave height. However, the contact force in radial direction is still important and of comparable magnitude to that of the vertical contact force. This highlights the importance of considering in-plane motions, as they directly determine the loads at the connection between membrane and floater, critical in the design of floating solar islands. A variation of the pretension, T_0 , indicates for what conditions the radial contact force can become larger than the given pretension. This implies a slack membrane, violating the premise of a linear-elastic model. While this may imply the need for more costly and time-consuming analyses (such as finite element analysis), the simple and efficient linear frequency domain model presented here can serve as a benchmark and validation tool for future, more complex models, and provide physically consistent estimates of connection loads under conditions within the linear-elastic range.

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